

Work Package 8 Ethics Deliverables summary

In the framework of ARISE Work Package 8 activities on oversight and fulfillment of the ethics requirements of the whole project, the following documents have been drafted and submitted as project deliverables:

- Deliverable 8.1 aims at fulfilling the Ethics Requirement asking to submit *“Copies of opinions/approvals by ethics committees and/or competent authorities for the research with humans”*.
- Deliverable 8.2 aims at fulfilling the Ethics Requirement asking to submit for each clinical study, prior to enrolment of first study subject, the *“(i) Final version of study protocol as submitted to regulators/ethics committee(s) (ii) Registration number of clinical study in a WHO-or ICMJE- approved registry (with the possibility to post results) (iii) Approvals (ethics committees and national competent authority if applicable) required for invitation/ enrolment of first subject in at least one clinical centre.”*
- Deliverable 8.3 aims at fulfilling the Ethics Requirement asking to submit for each clinical study *“a report on the status of posting results in the study registry(s), including timelines if/when final posting of results is scheduled after end of funding period”*.
- Deliverable 8.4 aims at fulfilling the Ethics Requirement asking to submit *“Copies of relevant documents for using, producing or collecting human cells or tissues (e.g., ethics approval, import licence, accreditation/designation/authorisation/licensing)”*.
- Deliverable 8.5 aims at fulfilling the Ethics Requirement asking to submit *“Copies of import/export authorisations, as required by national/EU legislation”*. The transfer of biological samples might require licensing procedures which imply the obtaining of import and export licenses by the government or the appointed competent authority for bringing or taking goods outside the country respectively.
- Deliverable 8.6 aims at fulfilling the Ethics Requirement asking to submit *“Copies of ethics approvals/authorisations/security clearances (if applicable)”* to prevent misuse of research findings.
- Deliverable 8.7 reports the appointment of the Ethics Advisor, in charge to oversee the ethical aspects of the ARISE project.
- Deliverable 8.8 aims at fulfilling the Ethics Requirement referred to the appointment of a Data Protection Officer (DPO) or the development of a data protection policy by the host institutions of the project. Specifically, *“the host institution must confirm that it has appointed a DPO and the contact details of the DPO are made available to all data subjects involved in the research. For host institutions not required to appoint a DPO under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) a detailed data protection policy for the project must be submitted kept on file.”*
- Deliverable 8.9 aims at fulfilling the Ethics Requirement referred to the *“evaluation of the ethics risks related to the data processing activities of the project. This includes also an opinion if a data protection impact assessment should be conducted under art.35 General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679. The risk evaluation and the opinion must be submitted as a deliverable.”* Planned and ongoing data processing activities of the project were identified and analysed, starting from the activities described in the Description

of Action (DoA). An evaluation of the related ethics risks was performed, as well as a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), Reg. (EU) 2016/679, was conducted for the data processing activities which met the criteria stated in Article 35.

All the project activities have been periodically evaluated and checked and deliverables have been updated accordingly.

